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Research Article

**TYPES OF TRAUMA IN DIFFERENT SEASONS IN
PATIENTS REFERRED TO EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT
OF MAYO HOSPITAL LAHORE**¹Dr Faria Afzal, ²Dr Junaid Afzal, ³Dr Ghulam Jamil¹JIANGXI University of Traditional Chinese Medicine, China²JIANGXI University of Traditional Chinese Medicine, China³ I.K.Akhunbaev Kyrgyz State Medical Academy (Bishkek Kyrgyzstan)**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: Trauma is a disease of modern societies and is one of the causes of death at any age in these societies. It is estimated that around 8.5 million people worldwide die each year as a result of trauma each year. Road accidents are more common among the types of injuries in the world. We conducted this study to compare the types of injuries at different times of the year in patients admitted to the emergency department of Mayo Hospital Lahore.

Methods: In this cross-sectional study, all trauma patients admitted to the Emergency Department of Mayo Hospital Lahore were enrolled in the study. This study does not highlight the diagnosis and treatment of diseases, as a source we use epidemiological data related to history and physical examination. Identifying statistics such as frequency, percentage, average, and standard deviation are used to analyze data. All data was analyzed using SPSS version 15.0.

Results: Out of 23,876 patients, 18,044 (75.6%) were male and 5832 (24.4%) were women. In most cases of injury, the incidence was 11.2% (2671) and was observed in September. Road accidents were the most common cause of injury in patients with an incidence of 33.9% (8095). He had a head injury of 38.6%. There was no correlation between age, gender, type of lesions in the patient and the sick limb.

Conclusion: The results showed that trauma is more common in men and young people. Therefore, adequate planning and strict traffic regulations can reduce the number of accidents.

Keywords: Trauma, Imam Reza, Different Seasons

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INTRODUCTION:

Trauma is a disease of modern societies and is one of the causes of death at any age in these societies. It is estimated that around 8.5 million people worldwide die each year as a result of trauma each year. The injury can be divided into four main classes of trauma mechanism: blunt trauma, penetrating injury, ruptured trauma and temperature trauma. Similar damage caused by trauma can be different in adults and children. Fifty percent of deaths among 1-14-year-olds are caused by injuries caused by road accidents. This is associated with the head injury that is most affected in children. As a global problem, widespread injuries are increasingly emerging. About 16,000 people worldwide died every day from various injuries and injuries, as the third leading cause of death is common among people aged 1 to 40. According to evidence published by the World Health Organization (WHO), road accidents among different types of insults around the world are the funniest, with around 25% of road accident deaths. In addition, data show that injuries are the leading cause of death and are morbid in children and adolescents in the United States. In this country, involuntary falls are the second most common cause of death in the category of injuries. Although road accidents are the most important cause of trauma, the decline in the number of older people is more common; On the other hand, accidents involving pedestrians are less common. In general, older people are more likely to be injured than young people in their daily work. A third of older people fall every year and a quarter of them suffer serious injuries. Usually drugs fall due to visual and cognitive disorders, stroke and arthritis. Trauma is usually the fifth leading cause of death among people over the age of 65. Given the large number of injuries experienced in developing countries, as well as the large number of accidents

in Iran, it aims to compare the types of injuries at different times of the year in patients admitted to the Imam Reza hospital trauma center in Tabriz.

METHODS:

In this cross-sectional study, all trauma patients admitted to Accident and Emergency department of Mayo Hospital Lahore were selected for one-year duration from May 2019 to May 2020. The inclusion criteria include all parents who applied to the emergency department of Imam Riza Hospital due to injury. Exclusion criteria include committee documents and records of patients with injuries with life signs accepted for the emergency department. This study does not highlight the diagnosis and treatment of diseases, as a source we use epidemiological data related to history and physical examination. Identifying statistics such as frequency, percentage, average, and standard deviation are used to analyze data. In addition, analytical tests such as pearson correlation were used in appropriate locations. All data was analyzed using SPSS version 15.0. P values below 0.05 were considered significant.

RESULTS:

The study included all patients with serious injuries who went to the emergency room. Patients who left the hospital were excluded. Of the 23,876 patients, 18,044 (75.6%) were men and 5,832 (24.4%), were women. Majority (31.7%) lowest prevalence aged 50-60 years and over 60 years (5%).

Figure 1 shows that the majority of injuries have an incidence of 11.2% (2,671). In general, the frequency of the injury from lowest to lowest is as follows: In the second quarter (30%), in the first quarter (29.9%), in the third quarter (24.2%) quarter (15.8%).

Figure 1. Frequency of trauma patients by month and season of the year.

Figure 2. Frequency graph of organs injuries.

Table 1 explains the occurrence of different types of injuries. Road accidents are the most common cause of injuries with an incidence of 33.9% (8095). After the accidents, 27.2% (6505) stumbles were reported. In addition, the decrease was 10.5% (2510) and was frequent. Conflicts, head trauma, gunshot wounds, tearing, chest injury, jury, abdominal injury, CO poisoning, electric shock and stabbing are the lowest incidence (less than 10%).

Table 1. Prevalence of type of trauma

Type of trauma	No. of patients	Percent
Driving accidents	8095	33.9
Stumble	6505	27.2
Fall from height	2510	10.5
Conflict	2302	9.6
Head trauma	1654	6.9
Motorcyclists accident	767	3.2
Injury caused by bullet	520	2.2
Laceration	489	2
Chest trauma	286	1.2
Pedestrian injury	224	0.9
Abdominal trauma	222	0.9
CO poisoning	212	0.9
Electrocution	53	0.2
Injury caused by knife	37	0.2

As shown in Figure 2, the most affected organ was a police officer with 38.6% of the incidence. Upper limb injuries accounted for 16.8%, lower limbs and chest incidence 11.9%. However, neck trauma had the lowest incidence (5.9%).

Figure 3. The consequence of trauma patients admitted to the emergency department.**DISCUSSION:**

In Iran, as in other countries, injuries caused by trauma are the leading cause of death in the population. In this study, men had more injuries (51.2%). This finding is consistent with other studies. In our study, most patients were between the ages of 20 and 30 years old. Similarly, the majority of patients in Patil et al were found between the ages of 20 and 29. The results showed that in 2013, most of the injury cases occurred in September, and the safest month was March. In the second trimester of the year, the high incidence of injuries compared to other seasons can be caused by holidays. Most cases of injury lasted until road accidents. Research shows that the injury is mainly caused by road accidents, which is in line with our discovery. Villaveces and the bow also saw that trauma was the main cause of the fall. Most often, the damaged organs were the limbs of the head and upper limbs. Fischler and Ráthlisberger observed that most snowboarders were injured in their work. However, the most commonly damaged organs in a study conducted in Turkey are the feet and ankles. In this study, lower limb fractures and shoulder dislocation occurred in the second stage. Patil and arc also concluded that fractures, lower limbs, upper limbs and head fractures were more common in 190 cases of road accidents. In our study, 81.8% of patients were discharged, 9.1% were hospitalized, 8.9% were targeted and a mortality rate of 0.1% was detected. Roudsari et al. It was shown that 94.9% of patients with injuries were discharged and 5.1% died.

CONCLUSION:

According to the results of our study, the incidence of traumatic events is higher among men and young people. In addition, it turned out that traffic accidents are the main cause of injuries. The injuries occurred in September. We can conclude that proper planning and strict traffic standards can reduce the rate of injuries. Similarly, these measures can improve health and have an impact on social and economic issues.

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